

SEAGRASS CITIZEN SCIENCE MONITORING PROTOCOL

for School and Community

COMMISSION DE
L'Océan Indien

Seychelles
Parks and Gardens
Authority

FOND FRANÇAIS POUR
L'ENVIRONNEMENT MONDIAL

AFD
AGENCE FRANÇAISE
DE DÉVELOPPEMENT

DEVELOP AND PILOT A CITIZEN SCIENCE–BASED SEAGRASS MONITORING AND RESTORATION PROTOCOL TO SUPPORT NATURAL REGENERATION AT CÔTE D'OR, PRASLIN

Prepared for: Government of Seychelles

Prepared by: Léo Barret & Gilberte Gendron, Bee Ecological Consulting

Date: 26/02/2026

INTRODUCTION	2
PARTNERS	3
WHEN AND WHERE TO MONITOR	5
WHEN TO MONITOR	5
WHERE TO MONITOR	5
SEAGRASS MONITORING PROTOCOL	6
APPROACH AND RECOMMENDED METHODS	6
SCHOOL GROUPS AND ECO-CLUB	7
COMMUNITY MEMBERS, NGOS, AND TOURISTS	16
EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS	20
GLOSSARY	20
ACTIVITY 1 - INTRODUCTION TO SEYCHELLES SEAGRASS SPECIES	21
ACTIVITY 2 – LOCAL THREATS TO SEAGRASS	30
ACTIVITY 3 – SEAGRASS BIODIVERSITY IDENTIFICATION	41

INTRODUCTION

Seychelles' coastal ecosystems are among the most biologically rich and economically valuable in the Western Indian Ocean. Coral reefs, mangroves, and seagrass meadows underpin fisheries, tourism, shoreline stability, and climate regulation, while supporting the livelihoods and wellbeing of island communities. In bays such as Côte d'Or (Anse Volbert), Praslin, shallow seagrass meadows form a critical interface between land and sea, providing nursery habitat for fish and invertebrates, stabilising sediments, improving water clarity, storing blue carbon, and buffering coastlines against erosion and wave action.

Despite their importance, seagrass meadows in Seychelles are increasingly exposed to localised pressures, including coastal development, anchoring, trampling, nutrient inputs, and growing tourism use, as well as climate-related stressors such as rising sea levels, higher sea surface temperatures, and more frequent extreme weather events. The degradation or loss of seagrass reduces natural coastal protection, increases vulnerability to erosion and flooding, and weakens the resilience of connected ecosystems such as coral reefs and mangroves.

At the same time, young people in Seychelles face limited access to hands-on, place-based environmental learning opportunities, particularly in marine science and coastal stewardship. While the ocean is central to national identity and the Blue Economy, opportunities to engage students directly in observing, understanding, and caring for nearby marine ecosystems remain uneven.

This creates a clear opportunity to address environmental and educational needs together. Engaging students, communities, and visitors in simple, well-designed seagrass monitoring activities strengthens awareness of coastal ecosystems while building practical skills, curiosity, and stewardship. In Côte d'Or, where seagrass meadows are highly visible, accessible, and closely linked to daily life, schools and community groups are uniquely positioned to observe change, document pressures, and contribute to collective care of the bay.

Within this context, the RECOS project has developed a community, school, and citizen seagrass monitoring protocol that fits within the national seagrass monitoring framework coordinated by SeyCCAT. The protocol emphasises low-impact observation, inclusivity, and learning-by-doing. By linking seagrass monitoring with education, culture, and coastal use, the protocol aims to strengthen local stewardship, support national conservation objectives, and help ensure that Seychelles' seagrass meadows continue to protect coastlines, sustain biodiversity, and support communities in a changing climate.

PARTNERS

Successful implementation of this protocol relies on strong collaboration between educational institutions, communities, practitioners, and authorities. The RECOS project promotes a partnership-based approach to ensure scientific credibility, broad participation, and long-term sustainability, while remaining aligned with the national seagrass monitoring framework coordinated by SeyCCAT.

Key partner categories include:

SCHOOLS AND EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMMES

Primary and secondary schools, Eco-Schools, Eco-Clubs, Wildlife Clubs, and programmes such as PAREO/AMEO play a central role in embedding the protocol within formal and informal education. Teachers and trained facilitators supervise activities, integrate monitoring into learning objectives, and support repeated engagement with local seagrass meadows.

GOVERNMENT AGENCIES AND PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS

National and local authorities, including MACCE, SPGA, and BERI, provide institutional support, policy alignment, and access to designated sites such as Educational Marine Areas. Their involvement ensures that citizen observations are consistent with management priorities and contribute to national datasets and reporting needs.

COMMUNITY ORGANISATIONS AND NGOS

Local NGOs, community groups, and conservation organisations support outreach, training, and coordination with volunteers. These partners are essential for fostering long-term stewardship, maintaining local relevance, and ensuring continuity beyond individual school programmes

PRIVATE SECTOR AND TOURISM OPERATORS

Tourism and excursion operators, such as those active in Côte d'Or, can support implementation by facilitating access to sites, sharing information with visitors, and promoting responsible practices. Their participation helps extend awareness beyond schools to the wider public and visitor community.

RESEARCH AND TECHNICAL PARTNERS

Universities, research institutions, and environmental consultants support protocol development, training, and data quality assurance. Their role is to ensure that methods remain scientifically robust and aligned with national and regional monitoring standards.

WHO CAN USE THIS PROTOCOL

This protocol is designed for broad, inclusive use, while maintaining clear guidance on roles and responsibilities to ensure safety, data quality, and positive learning outcomes. It is suitable for the following user groups:

1. SCHOOL GROUPS (AGES 8–14)

The protocol is primarily designed for upper primary and early secondary students participating through schools, Eco-Clubs, Wildlife Clubs, or Educational Marine Area (EMA) programmes. Activities must always be carried out under the supervision of teachers or trained facilitators. The approach is child-friendly and low-impact, requiring no advanced scientific skills only curiosity, basic swimming or wading ability where relevant, and respect for the marine environment. Older students (approximately 14 years and above) may progressively engage with more structured elements of national monitoring protocols under guidance.

2. COMMUNITY MEMBERS AND NGOS

Community volunteers, youth groups, and local NGOs can use the protocol to document seagrass presence, condition, and visible pressures in accessible coastal areas. Their involvement strengthens local ownership and provides valuable observations from sites that may not be covered by formal scientific surveys.

3. TOURISM OPERATORS AND VISITORS

Tourism operators, guides, and interested visitors can apply simplified elements of the protocol to observe and document seagrass during low-impact activities such as snorkelling or shallow-water exploration. When appropriate, observations may be shared through approved citizen-science platforms, contributing to broader awareness and monitoring efforts.

Across all user groups, the protocol emphasises observation rather than disturbance, safety always, and alignment with the national seagrass monitoring framework. By enabling diverse users to participate in a consistent and responsible way, the protocol helps link education, stewardship, and citizen science to long-term seagrass conservation in Seychelles

WHEN AND WHERE TO MONITOR

When to Monitor

Monitoring should take place during daytime, at low tide and under calm, safe weather conditions. Low tide means the meadow is shallow and accessible for students, improving visibility and safety.

Check tide tables and weather forecasts beforehand. Available here: <https://tides4fishing.com/sc/mahe/victoria>.

Avoid strong winds, heavy rain, storms, or poor water clarity.

Monitoring can be conducted once per school term or at least twice a year, with the ideal being a regular, predictable schedule (e.g., quarterly) to allow comparison across seasons and years.

Where to Monitor

Select a shallow, easily accessible seagrass meadow within or adjacent to Educational Marine Area (EMA).

Prefer sheltered bays, lagoons, or intertidal flats with knee- to waist-deep water and gentle conditions (no strong currents or heavy boat traffic).

If the EMA has a designated study zone, use it; otherwise choose a representative seagrass patch that can be revisited consistently, close to community;

Create simple shore-based reference points (e.g., aligning with a tree, rock, or building) to relocate the same area without GPS.

Schools or facilitators should ensure that all necessary permissions are secured if the site lies within a marine park or protected area.

Keep the study area small and manageable for children (10 m × 10 m section), so groups remain supervised and can complete activities without fatigue or dispersal.

Teacher / Facilitator Tasks

Arrange permissions, confirm site access, tides, transport, and review safety procedures.

SEAGRASS MONITORING PROTOCOL

Approach and Recommended Methods

This protocol applies two complementary approaches to seagrass monitoring, adapted to different user groups while remaining fully aligned with the RECOS project and the Seychelles National Seagrass Monitoring Framework (Tier 1).

1) SCHOOL GROUPS AND ECO-CLUBS (AGES 8–14)

School-based monitoring uses a simplified field protocol suitable for children aged 8–14, focusing on seagrass presence, morphotypes, percent cover, and general meadow condition using paper datasheets and simple tools. Older students ($\approx 14+$) may progressively transition to elements of the national Sentinel Site Monitoring Protocol (Tier 2).

Monitoring activity should be preceded by three classroom and field activities 1) Introduction to Seagrass, 2) Benefits of Seagrass, and 3) Threats to Seagrass which build essential knowledge, vocabulary, and observation skills using locally relevant examples from Côte d’Or and Seychelles lagoons. This preparation ensures that field monitoring is a meaningful extension of classroom learning and strengthens stewardship values.

2) COMMUNITY MEMBERS, NGOs, AND TOURISTS

Citizen-science monitoring for adults and visitors is implemented through GPS-enabled digital recording, with direct data entry into SeagrassSpotter. Each observation records site details, seagrass presence/absence, dominant species, and photographic evidence of disturbances (e.g. anchoring, algal blooms, litter, sedimentation, grazing). Records are quality-checked by the Seychelles National Focal Point for Seagrass Monitoring and integrated into the National Seagrass Repository, ensuring validated, interoperable data at national and global levels.

PREPARATION (BEFORE THE FIELD TRIP / CLASSROOM SESSION)

Introduction (10 minutes)

1. Explain that learners will act as “*seagrass scientists*” and contribute to real monitoring.
2. Show images of local seagrass morphotypes and explain the morphotype-based approach.

Organisation and Planning (10 minutes)

3. Explain the survey plan: learners will sample 3–5 spots within a seagrass meadow.
4. Divide learners into small teams (2–3 students per team).
5. Assign clear roles:
 - a. *Leader*: carefully places the quadrat at the sampling point and checks that it is positioned correctly without disturbing the seagrass or sediment
 - b. *Measurer*: estimates and measures seagrass parameters within the quadrat, including percent cover and seagrass height, using the guide and ruler.
 - c. *Recorder*: accurately records all observations and measurements on the datasheet, ensuring information is clear and complete.
6. Review the datasheet together so everyone understands what will be recorded.

Materials Check (5 minutes)

7. Quadrat frame, rulers, ID cards, percent-cover guides, clipboards, datasheets, Snorkel mask

Equipment List

All materials are low-cost and non-electronic, suitable for a simple field kit

**1 × standard quadrat
(50 × 50 cm)**

This is a square frame to outline sampling spots.

It can be made from PVC pipes, wood, or even four sticks and string. You can mark it with string into smaller grid squares (e.g. 5 cm or 10 cm divisions) to help estimate percentages.

**Monitoring
datasheets
(waterproof paper or
slates)**

Simple seagrass monitoring data sheets printed on paper and laminated for waterproofing. These should have spaces to record the date, location, names of participants, weather/tide, and for each quadrat: seagrass presence, species name(s), estimated percent cover and any notes.

Pencils

Carry pencils, pens may not write when paper is damp.

Ruler

Simple ruler to measure canopy height

Snorkel mask

Snorkel masks or swim goggles can be helpful for students to look underwater at the seagrass (especially for older or confident swimmers), but they are not required if the water is shallow and clear.

Proper footwear

Proper footwear (old sneakers, reef shoes or sandals with straps) to prevent cuts from shells or coral, and to avoid slipping

**Seagrass
identification sheet**

A one-page Seagrass Identification sheet with pictures of the common seagrass species (laminated for waterproofing).

FIELD SESSION AT THE SEAGRASS SITE

Site Briefing (5 minutes)

8. Gather learners and clearly identify:
 - a. The boundaries of the study area
 - b. Safe zones for movement
9. Review key safety rules (walking carefully, no running, no pulling plants).
10. Explain the general layout of the meadow using visible landmarks (rocks, trees, shoreline).
11. Check that all learners have their equipment and sun protection.

Demonstration (10 minutes)

Setting Up the Survey

12. Explain sampling approach:
 - a. Random sampling: place quadrats at spaced intervals using simple methods (step-and-place, leap-frog method).
 - b. Emphasise that all quadrats count, even if there is no seagrass (0% cover is valid data).

Quadrat Placement

13. Demonstrate how to gently place the quadrat without disturbing the sediment.

Figure 1. Survey layout used for the monitoring. The red outline shows the seagrass site selected for monitoring. Each colour represents a different student team (2-3 children per team). Teams place their quadrats from the shallow nearshore area toward deeper part

Hands-on Activity (30–45 minutes)

For each quadrat, teams complete the following steps:

Step 1: Seagrass Presence and Morphotype

- Record whether seagrass is present or absent.
- Identify the dominant morphotype using ID card
- Record one or more morphotypes if mixed.

Quadrat

ID Card

Step 2: Percent Cover Estimation

- Stand directly above the quadrat.
- Estimate how much of the ground is covered by seagrass:
- Use percentage values or simple categories (0–25%, 25–50%, 50–75%, 75–100%).
- Encourage discussion and agreement within the group before recording.

Step 3: Additional Observations

Check and Note:

- Presence of animals (fish, sea cucumbers, crabs, starfish) within the quadrat or around
- Physical damage (anchor scars, prop marks, trampling, mooring circle)
- Seagrass flowers or fruit present
- Pollution
- Water color
- Any other observations

Step 4: Repeat Sampling

- Move to the next location and repeat observations.
- Ensure quadrats are spread across the meadow (shallow edge, centre, deeper edge if possible).

Wider Site Survey (10 minutes)

After quadrat sampling, conduct a general scan of the area:

- Physical damage: anchor scars, propeller marks, mooring circles
- Seagrass flower or fruit presence/absence
- Pollution: plastics, fishing lines, debris (remove safely if possible)
- Water quality: clear, slightly turbid, very turbid; unusual smells
- Grazing signs: cropped leaves or grazed patches
- General observations: differences between areas, patterns noticed by learners

Example: Gomon Gran Fey (*Enhalus Acoroides*) female flower (top) and issected mature fruits with developed seeds (below).

Data Analysis and Discussion (20 minutes)

Encourage learners to share their findings and compare results between teams. Ask learners to describe what they observed within their quadrats, including seagrass cover, animals, and overall biodiversity. Discuss any challenges they experienced, such as estimating percent cover. Use this discussion to explain how quadrat sampling can help track changes in ecosystems over time, including plant growth, disturbance, or restoration.

Guiding questions may include:

- What did you notice about the seagrass in different parts of the meadow?
- Were some areas thicker or healthier than others? Why do you think that is?
- What patterns, if any, did you observe?
- How might environmental factors influence where organisms are found?
- What are the strengths and limitations of quadrat sampling?

What could be improved if the activity were repeated?

Explain in simple terms that scientists use small samples to understand larger patterns and that no single survey captures everything. Discuss key limitations, such as the number and placement of quadrats and the movement of animals in and out of the sampling area.

If time allows, compare results from different groups or sampling locations and discuss why the numbers may differ. Reinforce that natural variation is expected and that repeated monitoring over time helps Eco-Clubs and schools better understand changes in their local seagrass meadow.

Seychelles Seagrass Morphotypes and species

Flat straplike leaves

Thalassia hemprichii

Oceana serrulata

Halodule uninervis

Gomon Zerb Torti

Very Long leaves (min. 30 cm)

Enhalus acoroides

Gomon zerb gran fey

Spaghetti-like leaves

Syringodium isoetifolium

Gomon zerb spageti

Leaves in fanlike clusters

Thalassodendron ciliatum

Gomon zerb levantay

Oval leaves in pairs

Halophila decipiens

Gomon zerb zorey lapen

Community Members, NGOs, and Tourists

Citizen-science monitoring shall be implemented using a GPS-enabled SmartPhone . The most suitable method is the sampling and data entering directly into SeagrassSpotter .

Each Seagrassspotter observation will record:

1. Site information: observer, date, GPS coordinates, location name;
2. Presence/absence of seagrass;
3. Dominant species identified (seagrass spotter offers an identification tools)
4. Photographic evidence of disturbance indicators: anchor scars, algal blooms, litter, sedimentation, grazing, anchor.

Submitted records would be reviewed from the open access SeagrassSpotter database by the Seychelles National Focal Point for Seagrass Monitoring, which performs quality-assurance and validation checks. Verified data are integrated into the National Seagrass Repository and synchronised with the global SeagrassSpotter database, ensuring interoperability and long-term storage.

SeagrassSpotter is a global citizen-science platform, accessible via website and mobile application that enables users to record and share georeferenced photographs of seagrass observations. Contributors can identify seagrasses to species level and provide optional details on habitat characteristics such as morphology, associated fauna, visible threats, and human use. The platform is designed for ease of participation and requires no prior training: users are guided through species identification and can indicate their level of confidence (“not confident,” “somewhat,” “very,” or “certain”).

Each submission is reviewed monthly by expert validators and experienced seagrass researchers to ensure data accuracy and consistency. Records found to be misidentified or located outside expected seagrass distribution ranges are flagged and excluded from the verified dataset. Validated observations contribute to an open-access global database supporting seagrass research, conservation, and education efforts across multiple spatial scales.

Project Seagrass (2020). SeagrassSpotter: A Citizen Science Platform for Global Seagrass Monitoring. Project Seagrass, Cardiff University. Available at: www.seagrassspotter.org

Outcomes

The expected outcomes of this citizen-science approach include:

1. Empowered citizens and communities actively engaged in seagrass stewardship, contributing local knowledge and observations that strengthen national monitoring and management efforts.
2. A shared national baseline on seagrass distribution and condition across Seychelles' Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ), derived from verified community-based observations.
3. A comprehensive geo-referenced photographic database, hosted on SeagrassSpotter and mirrored within the National Seagrass Data Repository, ensuring open access, traceability, and long-term data management.
4. Increased national and international visibility of Seychelles' seagrass ecosystems through integration of citizen-generated data into global conservation platforms and networks, including Project Seagrass, UNEP, and the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS).

Reporting and Data Sharing

All validated observations are archived within the SeagrassSpotter database and could be crosslinked with a National Seagrass Repository. Summary analyses and maps are produced annually as part of the National Seagrass Status Report and shared with regional and global initiatives, including WIOMSA, GOOS/MBON, and OBIS.

RESOURCES

The following resources are recommended to support education, awareness, and citizen science monitoring of seagrass meadows for children, schools, teachers, and community groups. They combine age-appropriate educational materials with scientifically credible references aligned with this protocol.

PROJECT SEAGRASS: A comprehensive online hub providing age-appropriate educational materials, lesson plans, activities, factsheets, and outreach tools focused on seagrass ecosystems. The resources are suitable for schools, teachers, Eco-Clubs, and community groups, and can be adapted for classroom use, field preparation, and awareness campaigns.

Link: <https://www.projectseagrass.org/education/>

BEGINNER'S GUIDE TO SEAGRASS: A short, illustrated introduction explaining what seagrass is, why it is important, and the main threats it faces. Well suited for classroom discussions and introductory lessons for children and community groups.

Link: <https://www.projectseagrass.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/Beginners-Guide-to-Seagrass.pdf>

INDO-PACIFIC SEAGRASS COLOURING BOOK (VOLUME 1): A child-friendly colouring book introducing seagrass-associated species (e.g. turtles, dugongs, fish, invertebrates) found in Indo-Pacific seagrass meadows. Particularly effective for younger learners (ages 6–10) and awareness activities.

Link: <https://www.projectseagrass.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Temperate-North-Atlantic-Colouring-Book-Volume-1.docx>

OUT OF THE BLUE – THE VALUE OF SEAGRASSES (UNEP): A comprehensive report highlighting the importance of seagrass ecosystems for climate mitigation, fisheries, coastal protection, and livelihoods. While detailed, its graphics and facts can support teachers and NGOs in developing lesson plans or community talks.

Link: <https://www.unep.org/resources/report/out-blue-value-seagrasses-environment-and-people>

GUIDELINES FOR SEAGRASS ECOSYSTEM RESTORATION IN THE WESTERN INDIAN OCEAN (WIOMSA/NAIROBI CONVENTION): handbook targeting resource managers, community organizations, and volunteers in the WIO region. It outlines step-by-step methods to design and implement successful seagrass restoration projects.

Link: <https://www.commissionoceanindien.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/Guidelines-for-Seagrass-Ecosystem-Restoration-in-the-Western-Indian-Ocean-Region.pdf>

SEAGRASS EDUCATOR'S HANDBOOK (SEAGRASS-WATCH): A teacher's handbook providing background on what seagrasses are, their anatomy, distribution, etc. It equips educators

with scientific knowledge and lesson ideas to communicate seagrass ecology to students.

Link: https://www.seagrasswatch.org/wp-content/uploads/Citizenscience/education/pdf/Seagrass_Educators_Handbook.pdf

SEAGRASS-WATCH ACTIVITY BOOKS: A set of printable activity booklets created by the Seagrass-Watch program for use in primary and middle schools. These contain puzzles, quizzes, and fun facts about seagrass habitats (e.g. a Year 1–4 “Seagrass Topic” activity book). Teachers and eco-club leaders can use them to engage children in learning about seagrass conservation through games and challenges.

Link: <https://www.seagrasswatch.org/education/>

SEAGRASS SPOTTER APP: A global citizen-science tool (mobile app and website) that lets anyone report seagrass sightings with photos. This free app empowers local communities, students, and even tourists to help map seagrass meadows. It’s an interactive way to involve the public in seagrass monitoring and is often used in citizen science programs.

Link: <https://www.seagrasswatch.org/seagrass-spotter/>

EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS

Glossary

Term	Definition
Algal blooms	A rapid increase in algae growth, often caused by excess nutrients in the water.
Angiosperms:	Angiosperms are plants which produce flowers, seeds and fruits. Some examples include passionfruit,
Biodiversity	The variety of life including all the different species living in an area.
Carbon sink	Natural or artificial environment viewed in terms of its ability to absorb carbon dioxide
Carbon storage	The process by which seagrass captures and stores carbon in sediments and plant material.
Disturbance	An event or activity that alters the natural environment, such as storms or human impacts.
Ecosystem	A system where living organisms (plants and animals) interact with each other and with their environment.
Grazing	Feeding activity where animals consume seagrass or algae.
Habitat	The natural environment where a species lives and grows.
Intertidal	The coastal zone that is alternately exposed and submerged by tides.
Invertebrates	Animals without backbone, including crabs, worms, and sea stars.
Monitoring	The regular collection of information to track changes in the environment over time.
Observations	Recorded notes of what is seen during fieldwork, including plants, animals, and conditions.
Percent cover	The proportion of the seabed covered by seagrass, measured as a percentage from 0 to 100%
Quadrat	A square sampling frame used to study and measure plants and animals in a fixed area.
Restoration	Actions taken to help damaged ecosystems recover and return to a healthy condition.
Seagrass	Marine flowering plants that grow underwater and have roots, leaves, and flowers.
Seagrass height	The length of seagrass leaves measured from the seabed to the leaf tip.
Seagrass meadows	A marine ecosystem where seagrass grows and forms the dominant habitat
Seagrass morphotypes	Different growth forms or shapes of seagrass, which can vary by species or conditions. Five morphotypes in Seychelles.
Seaweed	Marine algae that live in the sea but do not have roots, stems, or flowers.
Sedimentation	The process where particles like sand or mud settle on the seabed.
Subtidal	The marine zone that remains underwater at all times.
Tide	The movement of the sea level rising and falling each day due to the Moon and Sun.

Activity 1 - Introduction to Seychelles Seagrass Species

Target group: School groups and Eco-Clubs (ages 8–14)

Duration: 60 minutes (classroom or shaded outdoor space)

Setting: Classroom preparation prior to field monitoring

LEARNING OBJECTIVES

By the end of this activity, learners will be able to:

1. Explain what seagrass is and how it differs from seaweed.
2. Describe the role seagrass plays in Seychelles' marine ecosystems.
3. Recognise and correctly name common **seagrass morphotypes** using Creole names.
4. Understand that one morphotype can include several species, and that morphotype identification is sufficient for monitoring at school level.

KEY CONCEPTS

- Seagrasses are flowering plants that live underwater in shallow coastal areas.
- They have roots, rhizomes, leaves, flowers, and seeds, unlike seaweeds (algae).
- Seagrass meadows provide:
 - Habitat and nursery grounds for fish and invertebrates
 - Food for turtles and dugongs
 - Coastal protection by stabilising sediments
 - Carbon storage
- In this activity, learners will not identify species, but instead learn to recognise morphotypes, based on leaf shape and growth form.

LEARNING ACTIVITIES

What is Seagrass

Seagrasses (marine phanerogams) are flowering and seeding fruit-bearing plants (angiosperms) which are adapted to life in salt-water or brackish water and on sandy or muddy soils rich in organic material and calcium carbonate.

Seagrasses often grow in patches on the seafloor, but they can also extend to form large, dense meadows. Seagrass meadows may be composed of a single species (monospecific) or several different species (multispecific).

Seagrasses, like mangrove trees, are marine angiosperms (flowering plants). They evolved during the Cretaceous period, around 145 million years ago, from terrestrial angiosperms that adapted to life in aquatic environments. Seagrasses can live fully submerged in seawater. Their strong root systems anchor them to the substrate and help them withstand waves and currents. Like land plants, seagrasses produce pollen and seeds.

Seagrass meadows are fundamentally important ecosystems that help maintain the planet's ecological balance. They provide habitat, food, and shelter for many marine species, act as significant carbon sinks, and help reduce coastal erosion. Key functions are outlined below.

1. Interactions with mangrove forests and coral reefs

Mangrove forests, seagrass meadows, and coral reefs form interconnected coastal systems that interact to stabilize the nearshore environment. Seagrasses trap sediments and suspended particles with their roots and leaves, improving water clarity. Clear water is essential for both seagrasses and corals because both rely on photosynthesis. The oxygen produced through photosynthesis supports aerobic decomposition and nutrient recycling in coastal zones. Seagrass meadows also absorb large amounts of nutrients and function as natural filters for chemical substances. This filtering role helps maintain the balance between corals and macroalgae on reefs, since nutrient enrichment can drive excessive algal growth that can overgrow and smother corals. In addition, seagrass meadows are highly productive and export nutrients and biomass to adjacent ecosystems. Many fish and crustaceans use seagrasses during juvenile stages before moving to habitats such as coral reefs.

2. Primary productivity and biological diversity

Seagrass meadows are highly productive ecosystems that absorb large quantities of carbon dioxide and release oxygen through photosynthesis, contributing to long-term carbon storage. Alongside tropical and temperate forests, they are among the most productive ecosystems globally. Their productivity and structural complexity increase habitat diversity, supporting high levels of marine biodiversity.

3. Shelter, nursery habitat, and food for many species

Seagrass meadows support a wide range of organisms, including sea stars, sea urchins, and clams, which benefit from protection from waves and currents. They also serve as nursery areas for larval and juvenile stages of fishes, mollusks, lobsters, and other commercially important species. Seagrass leaves provide surfaces for epiphytic algae, sponges, foraminifera, and other organisms. Seagrasses are also associated with species of medical importance (Martínez Daranas, 2007). Seagrass leaves are a key food source for many marine animals, including manatees and green sea turtles—both listed as endangered. Plant fragmentation generates detritus that feeds seabed and shoreline organisms such as sea cucumbers, crabs, and anemones. As seagrass decomposes, nutrients are released into the water and can be

reabsorbed by seagrasses and utilized by plankton. Seabirds, including gulls and pelicans, often forage over seagrass meadows.

4. Erosion prevention and coastal protection

The extensive root and rhizome networks that anchor seagrasses help stabilize seabed sediments by promoting sediment accumulation, deposition, compaction, and overall substrate stabilization, thereby reducing seafloor erosion. Seagrass leaves also absorb and dissipate wave and current energy, helping protect shorelines from erosion. Their capacity to trap and retain sediments further supports water clarity, reinforcing the health of nearby seagrass and coral reef systems.

Introduction – What Do We Know About Seagrass? (5 minutes)

- Ask learners:
 - What do you think seagrass is?
 - Where have you seen it?
 - What animals might live there?
- Introduce key vocabulary: *ecosystem, habitat, biodiversity.*

Exploration – Understanding Seagrass and Seaweed

Step 1: Seagrass Biology

Explain that seagrass is a flowering plant adapted to life underwater. Use images or short videos showing seagrass meadows in Seychelles.

Step 2: Comparing Seagrass and Seaweed.

Using photographs and, where available, fresh specimens collected responsibly, guide learners to observe the main differences between seagrass and seaweed. Compare Seagrass and Seaweed morphology using images and fresh specimen

Create small team with each a bucket that include seaweed and seagrass, team members must create two separate bucket, one with seagrass and one with seaweed.

Step 3: Sorting Activity

Divide learners into small teams and provide each team with a bucket containing a mix of seagrass and seaweed samples. Ask each team to sort the material into **two separate buckets**: one for seagrass and one for seaweed.

Learners should discuss within their group why they placed each sample in a particular bucket, using the identification clues provided earlier.

SEAGRASS VERSUS SEAWEED

Feature	Seagrass	Seaweed (Algae)
What it is	A flowering plant	Algae
Roots	Has true roots and rhizomes that anchor it in the sediment	No true roots (attached by a holdfast or free-floating)
Leaves	Has leaves (long, flat, round, or oval depending on morphotype)	Has blade, not true leaves
Flowers & seeds	Yes – produces flowers, fruits, and seeds	No flowers or seeds

3. Seagrass Morphotypes Identification

Step 1: Introduction to Morphotypes

Introduce to Learners the following **six morphotypes**, which may each include several species:

1. **Gomon zerb gran fey** – very large, long ribbon-like leaves
2. **Gomon zerb levantay** – stiff, fan-shaped or upright leaves
3. **Gomon zerb spageti** – thin, round, spaghetti-like leaves
4. **Gomon zerb torti** – flat strap-like leaves forming dense meadows
5. **Gomon zerb pti fey oval/ zorey lapen** – small oval leaves in pairs

Step 2: Matching Activity (Group Work)

- Divide learners into small groups.
- Provide each group with a set of seagrass images.
- Ask learners to:
 - Match each image to the correct morphotype name.
 - Explain their choice based on leaf size, shape, and texture.

Step 3: Hands-on Identification Using Collected Samples

Using the seagrass bucket from Activity 2 (Exploration):

- Identify and classify the different morphotypes present in each bucket.
- Compare results between groups to identify how many morphotypes are present across all samples.
- For each morphotype:
 - Say the Creole name aloud.
 - Describe the leaf shape using simple terms (long, thin, round, oval, stiff, soft).
 - Ask learners to repeat the name and point out key identifying features.

Step 4/ Wrap-Up – What Have We Learned?

- Ask each learner to share:
 - One new thing they learned about seagrass
 - One morphotype name they remember
- Explain that during field monitoring, they will use these morphotypes to observe real seagrass meadows

SEAGRASS SPECIES AND MORPHOTYPES OF SEYCHELLES

Photo	Species	Description
	<p>Zerb Gomon Torti <i>Thalassia hemprichii</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strap-leaved forming dense meadows with long, curved, 3-veined blades • Often have short black bars of tannin cells in leaf blade. • The leaves grow from thick rhizomes with scars between shoots. It is common in shallow reef flat areas. It is amongst the favourite food of green turtles.
	<p>Zerb Gomon Torti <i>Oceana serrulata</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This species of seagrass has flat, narrow (5 - 9 mm wide), strap-like leaves of up to 50 cm with a serrated tip. • Leaf sheath is broadly triangular with a narrow base and the scars do not form continuous ring around the stem. • It grows on shallow reef flats and sand banks and one of the favourite foods of green turtles.
	<p>Zerb Gomon Torti <i>Halodule uninervis</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flat straplike narrow leaves with a distinctive trident-shaped tip. • The leaf has a single central longitudinal vein. • Its rhizomes are usually pale ivory, with clean black leaf scars. • It is common on shallow sandy or muddy areas and is the preferred food of dugongs.

Gomon zerb gran fey

Gomon zerb gran fey
Enhalus acoroides

- Very long ribbon-like leaves 30-150 cm long
- Thick roots (Rhizome) with long black bristles and cord-like roots
- Found on shallow/intertidal sand/mud banks (often adjacent to mangrove forests)
- Its leaf blades may float on surface at low tide and can easily entangled in boat propellers.
- It is an important habitat for herbivorous fish especially Rabbitfish.

Gomon zerb spageti / Gomon zerb sed

Gomon zerb spageti
Syringodium isoetifolium

- This species of seagrass is the only seagrass with round, tube-like “spaghetti” leaves (1 - 3 mm in diameter) ranging from 7 - 30 cm long. Its leaves tapers to a point.
- It grows on shallow reef flats and sand banks.

Gomon zerb levantay

Gomon zerb levantay
Thalassodendron ciliatum

- Its leaves (5 - 15 cm long) are arranged in fanlike clusters.
- The leaf clusters each comprise 6 - 20 leaves. This species of seagrass forms clumps of curved ribbon-like leaves growing from upright stems
- It can form dense meadows and is commonly found on rocky reef crests with strong waves.

Photo

Species

Description

Gomon zerb pti fey Oval /Gomon zerb zorey lapen / Gomon zerb papiyon

Gomon zerb pti fey
Halophila spp.

- Small, delicate oval shaped leaves (1 - 2.5cm long)
- arranged in pairs with a creeping bifurcated stem.
- It is usually found subtidal waters of less than 10 m.

Activity 2 – Local Threats to Seagrass

PART 1: UNDERSTANDING SEAGRASS THREATS (CLASSROOM)

Objective: Introduce the main human-related threats to seagrass meadows in Seychelles and explore simple ways to reduce these impacts.

Step 1: Introduction

Explain that seagrass meadows are vulnerable to human activities, especially in shallow coastal areas. Introduce the five main threats:

- Coastal development
- Anchoring
- Boat propellers
- Pollution from nutrient run-off
- Plastic pollution

Use simple images or drawings to illustrate each threat.

Step 2: Local Context Discussion

Ask learners:

- Which of these threats might occur near our community or school?
- Which ones are linked to everyday human activities?
- Who can help reduce these impacts (boat users, communities, planners, tourists)?

Explain that during the field visit, they will **look for signs of these threats**, not cause them.

PART 2: SPOTTING THREATS IN THE SEAGRASS MEADOW (FIELD ACTIVITY)

Objective: Help learners recognise visible signs of seagrass disturbance and link them to human activities.

Step 1: Observation Walk

At the seagrass site (or along the beach):

- Walk slowly along the edge of the meadow.
- Ask learners to look for and point out:
 - Anchor scars or bare patches
 - Propeller scars (long straight lines)
 - Plastic litter on or near seagrass
 - Cloudy or muddy water
 - Coastal structures (jetties, seawalls, reclaimed land)

Learners do **not touch or disturb** the seagrass.

Step 2: Linking Cause and Effect

Gather learners and discuss:

- What did we observe?
- Which threats do these signs relate to?
- How might these impacts affect seagrass growth over time?

Encourage learners to think about **long-term effects**, such as slow recovery and loss of habitat for fish and turtles.

Wrap-Up: From Observation to Action (5 minutes)

Conclude by reinforcing key messages:

- Seagrass grows slowly and damage can last many years.
- Small actions (correct anchoring, waste reduction, careful boating) make a big difference.
- Monitoring and reporting help protect seagrass.

Ask each learner to share:

- One threat they remember
- One action that can help protect seagrass

Coastal Development as a Threat to Seagrass

Habitat Loss

Development destroys and replaces seagrass meadows.

Reclamation

Sedimentation

Polluted runoff from construction and urban areas introduces silt.

Declining Water Quality

Pollution and runoff increase nutrient levels and reduce water clarity.

Dredging

Dredging tears up seagrass beds and makes the water cloudy with sediment.

Changes in Water Movement

Changes in water movement from coastal structures increase sedimentation and erosion.

Habitat Loss

Development destroys and replaces seagrass meadows.

Dredging

Dredging tears up seagrass beds and makes the water cloudy with sediment.

Reclamation

Reclamation fills in seagrass habitat, replacing it with land and polluting nearby waters.

Changes in Water Movement

Changes in water movement from coastal structures increase sedimentation and erosion.

COASTAL DEVELOPMENT

Impact

One of the main impacts of coastal development is habitat loss. When coastal areas are dredged or reclaimed, seagrass meadows are directly impacted. It often leads to increased sedimentation in the water. Land clearing and construction disturb soil, which can wash into the sea during rainfall. Suspended sediments make the water cloudy and reduce the amount of sunlight reaching seagrass leaves. Since seagrass relies on sunlight to make food through photosynthesis, reduced light can slow growth and eventually cause seagrass to die. Changes to the natural movement of water caused by coastal structures such as seawalls, jetties and reclaimed land can further harm seagrass. Altered currents may increase erosion in some areas and cause sediment build-up in others, creating unsuitable conditions for seagrass growth.

How to mitigate threats

Protecting seagrass ecosystems requires careful planning of coastal development projects. Environmental impact assessments, the use of buffer zones, and avoiding dredging or reclamation near seagrass meadows can help reduce damage.

Anchoring as a Threat to Seagrass

Anchor Damage

Dropping an anchor can tear up, break, and bury seagrass, creating scars in meadows.

Slow Recovery

Scars may take years to heal, causing long-term loss of seagrass habitat.

Chain Scarring

Dragging anchor chains scrape, cut, and uproot seagrass over a larger area.

Loss of Habitat

Damage reduces habitat and food for marine life and diminishes natural protection.

ANCHORING

Impact	How to mitigate threats
<p>Anchoring can cause serious damage to seagrass habitats.</p> <p>When anchors are dropped onto the seabed, they can directly uproot seagrass plants, breaking leaves and damaging the underground rhizomes that hold the plants in place. Repeated anchoring in the same area can result in large bare patches where seagrass struggles to recover.</p> <p>The movement of anchor chains causes additional harm. As boats swing with wind and tides, the chain drags across the seabed, scraping and cutting seagrass shoots and disturbing sediments.</p> <p>Anchoring damage can take many years to heal. Seagrass grows slowly, and damaged rhizomes may not easily reconnect. In some cases, scars remain visible for decades, leading to long-term loss of habitat.</p>	<p>Reducing anchoring damage is possible through better management and awareness. Installing mooring buoys, designating no-anchoring zones over seagrass, and encouraging responsible boating practices can greatly reduce impacts. Protecting seagrass from anchoring helps ensure the long-term health of coastal ecosystems and the benefits they provide to both marine life and people.</p>

Boat Propellers as a Threat to Seagrass

Propeller Scars

Spinning propellers cut and uproot seagrass, leaving long, narrow scars.

Cloudy Water

Propellers stir up sediment, making the water cloudy and blocking sunlight.

Loss of Habitat

Damage reduces habitat and food for marine life and diminishes natural coastal protection.

BOAT PROPELLERS

Impact

Boat propellers are a significant and often overlooked threat to seagrass, especially in shallow coastal waters. When boats travel through shallow areas, propellers can cut directly into seagrass meadows, slicing leaves and damaging the underground rhizomes that anchor the plants to the seabed. This creates long, narrow scars known as propeller scars, which fragment seagrass beds and reduce their ability to recover naturally.

Propeller action also stirs up sediments, making the water cloudy. Increased turbidity reduces the amount of sunlight reaching seagrass leaves, limiting photosynthesis and slowing growth. Repeated disturbance prevents young shoots from re-establishing, leading to long-term degradation of the meadow. Seagrass grows slowly, and once rhizomes are cut, regrowth across scars is limited. Over time, frequent boat traffic can turn once-continuous seagrass meadows into patchy, degraded habitats.

How to mitigate threats

Preventing propeller damage is possible through responsible boating practices. Using marked navigation channels, reducing speed in shallow areas, trimming engines up, and installing seagrass-friendly propeller guards can significantly reduce harm.

Pollution – Nutrient Run-off as a Threat to Seagrass

POLLUTION – NUTRIENT RUN OFF

Impact

Nutrient run-off is one of the major pollution threats to seagrass ecosystems. It occurs when excess nutrients, mainly nitrogen and phosphorus, wash into coastal waters from land. These nutrients often come from agricultural fertilizers, sewage, animal waste, urban stormwater, and poorly treated wastewater.

When too many nutrients enter the sea, they cause excessive growth of algae. These algae can cover seagrass leaves, blocking sunlight that seagrass needs to photosynthesise and grow. Without enough light, seagrass becomes weak, grows slowly, and may eventually die.

Nutrient pollution can also lead to murky water, further reducing light penetration. When algal blooms die and decompose, they consume oxygen in the water, creating low-oxygen conditions that can stress or kill seagrass and the animals that depend on it.

How to mitigate threats

Reducing nutrient run-off through better waste management, proper sewage treatment, responsible fertilizer use, and protection of coastal buffer zones such as mangroves and wetlands is essential to protect seagrass.

Plastic Pollution Threatens Seagrass Ecosystems

Litter

Stormwater drains

Rivers

Poor waste management

Coastal tourism

Smothered Seagrass

Bags, bottles, and food wrappers settle on seagrass and block sunlight, reducing plant growth.

Entangled & Damaged Seagrass

Ropes and discarded fishing gear entangle seagrass, dragging across and damaging the plants.

Microplastics in Sediment

Plastics break down into microplastics that mix into sediment where seagrass roots grow. Tiny particles are ingested by small marine life, entering the food web.

Protecting seagrass from plastic pollution helps maintain healthy coastal ecosystems

Reduce plastic use

Improve waste management

Promote recycling

Organize clean-ups & raise public awareness

POLLUTION – PLASTIC

Impact

Plastics enter the ocean through littering, poor waste management, rivers, stormwater drains, fishing activities, and coastal tourism.

Large plastic items such as bags, bottles, food wrappers, fishing nets, and ropes can settle on seagrass meadows causing sunlight to be blocked, thus reducing photosynthesis and weakening the plants. Prolonged coverage can cause seagrass to die and leave bare patches on the seabed.

Plastics can also cause physical damage. Floating debris and discarded fishing gear may become entangled in seagrass leaves and rhizomes.

Over time, plastics break down into microplastics, which mix into the sediments where seagrass roots grow. Microplastics can change sediment structure, reduce oxygen availability, and negatively affect seagrass health. These tiny particles can also be ingested by small animals living in seagrass beds, entering the marine food web.

How to mitigate threats

Preventing plastic pollution is essential to protect seagrass ecosystems. Actions such as reducing plastic use, improving waste management, promoting recycling, organising clean-up activities, and raising public awareness can significantly reduce plastic entering the ocean.

Activity 3 – Seagrass Biodiversity identification

LEARNING OBJECTIVE:

- Learn how to identify marine species
- Practice observation, comparison, and classification skills
- Understand the diversity of organisms associated with seagrass ecosystems

Classroom (before field visit)

1. Review the identification sheet of species that can be found in seagrass meadows.
2. Learn the key characteristics for Identifying each species

Field Visit

Materials required:

- Printed ID guide sheets
 - Observation worksheet
 - Pencil / clipboard
 - Ruler for estimating size (Optional)
1. Visit a seagrass meadow. Explore the habitat by snorkelling and observe the various species you have learn in class. Take note of the characteristics you observe e.g. size, colour, texture and patterns.
 2. Fill in the observation worksheet for with key observation details (see form below).

Classroom (after field visit):

1. Draw and colour your favourite species you have observed
2. Present you drawing and findings to your colleagues
3. Describe which feature helped you most to identify this species?

MARINE SPECIES OBSERVATION WORKSHEET

Student Name(s): _____

Class / Group: _____

Date: _____

Instructions

Observe the organism carefully. Use the identification features to record what you see before deciding which species it is.

Observation Table

Observation features	What you observed
Body shape	_____
Size	<input type="checkbox"/> Small <input type="checkbox"/> Medium <input type="checkbox"/> Large
Main colour(s)	_____
Key features seen	<input type="checkbox"/> Arms <input type="checkbox"/> Shell <input type="checkbox"/> Fins <input type="checkbox"/> Flippers <input type="checkbox"/> Tentacles
Patterns / markings	<input type="checkbox"/> Marking spots <input type="checkbox"/> Lines <input type="checkbox"/> Knobs <input type="checkbox"/> Scutes
Texture (if visible)	<input type="checkbox"/> Smooth <input type="checkbox"/> Bumpy <input type="checkbox"/> Spiny <input type="checkbox"/> Leathery
Behaviour	<input type="checkbox"/> Resting <input type="checkbox"/> Swimming <input type="checkbox"/> Grazing <input type="checkbox"/> Buried

Identification

Possible species	Tick (✓)	Draw the main features you observed below
Starfish		
Sea cucumber		
Rabbitfish		
Emperor fish		
Macroalgae / Seaweed		
Ray		
Sea turtle		

Final Identified Species: _____

*(Repeat this worksheet for each species observed.)

IDENTIFICATION GUIDE OF ASSOCIATED BIODIVERSITY OF THE SEAGRASS BEDS

Species	Description
---------	-------------

Starfish

1. Body Shape and Number of Arms

Most starfish have five arms, but some species may have more or fewer. Arms can be long and slender or short and thick.

2. Size

Note the overall size from arm tip to arm tip. Starfish range from a few centimetres to over 40 cm across.

3. Colour and Patterns

Observe the colour (e.g. blue, orange, red, brown) and any patterns, spots, knobs, or spines, which are key identification features.

4. Surface Texture

Check whether the surface is smooth, bumpy, spiny, or covered with knobs. Texture often distinguishes similar-looking species.

Sea cucumber

1. Body Shape

Sea cucumbers have a long, cylindrical or sausage-shaped body, often lying on the seabed.

2. Size

They vary in size from small (10–15 cm) to large (over 40 cm), depending on the species.

3. Colour and Patterns

Common colours include brown, black, grey, green, or mottled, sometimes with spots or bands.

4. Skin Texture

The skin may be smooth, leathery, wrinkled, or covered with small bumps or papillae.

5. Feeding Tentacles

At one end of the body, look for small tentacles around the mouth, used for feeding on sand and organic matter.

Rabbitfish

1. Body Shape

Rabbitfish have a laterally compressed (flattened), oval-shaped body, giving them a disc-like appearance.

2. Head and Mouth

They have a small mouth with closely packed, incisor-like teeth, adapted for grazing on algae and seagrass.

3. Colour and Patterns

Colours range from silver, grey, brown to yellow, often with spots, lines, or mottled patterns. Some species change colour depending on mood or time of day.

4. Fins and Spines

Rabbitfish have strong dorsal and anal fin spines, which are venomous and should not be touched.

5. Size

Most rabbitfish grow to about 20–40 cm in length.

Emperor

1. Body Shape

Emperors have a robust, oval to slightly elongated body with a relatively large head.

2. Mouth and Teeth

They have a strong mouth with thick lips and visible teeth, adapted for feeding on crustaceans, molluscs, and small fish.

3. Colour and Markings

Colours vary from silver-grey to brown or yellowish, often with lines, spots, or facial markings. Some species show distinctive stripes or masks near the eyes.

4. Size

Most emperor fish are medium to large, typically 30–80 cm, depending on the species.

5. Fins

They have a single continuous dorsal fin and a slightly forked tail.

Macroalgae/ Seaweed

1. Overall Shape (Thallus Form)

Macroalgae may appear leaf-like, branched, bushy, filamentous, or fan-shaped. The overall form is often the first clue.

2. Colour Group

Identify the colour, which helps place it into a major group:

- Green algae – bright green
- Brown algae – brown, olive, or golden
- Red algae – red, purple, or pink (often appear dark underwater)

3. Size

Macroalgae range from small turf-like forms to large, conspicuous seaweeds.

4. Texture

Feel (only if permitted) or observe whether it is soft, leathery, slippery, or coarse.

5. Attachment

Look for a holdfast attaching the algae to rocks, coral rubble, or sometimes seagrass sediments.

Rays

1. Body Shape

Rays have a flat, disc-shaped body with wide pectoral fins that look like wings.

2. Tail

They have a long, whip-like tail, often much longer than the body. Some species have a venomous spine on the tail.

3. Eyes and Mouth Position

The eyes are on top of the body, while the mouth and gill slits are underneath, an important identification feature.

4. Colour and Patterns

Colours are usually grey, brown, or sandy, helping them blend in. Some species have spots or patterns, especially on the upper surface.

5. Size

Rays range from small (less than 50 cm) to very large species with wingspans over 2 metres.

Sea turtle

1. Shell Shape (Carapace)

Sea turtles have a hard, streamlined shell. Note its shape and pattern—some are more oval, others heart-shaped.

2. Scutes (Shell Plates)

Look at the number and arrangement of scutes on the shell, which is a key identification feature for different species.

3. Head Size and Shape

Head size varies by species: some have small, narrow heads, while others have large, broad heads with strong jaws.

4. Colour and Patterns

Shell and skin colours range from olive, brown, and green to reddish-brown, often with lighter or mottled patterns.

5. Flippers

Sea turtles have long, paddle-like flippers. Check the number of claws on the front flippers if visible.